

DETERMINANT OF INTENTION TO STAY AMONG INDONESIAN LECTURER: THE MEDIATING ROLE OF JOB SATISFACTION

SOPIAH^{1*}, HANDRI DIAN WAHYUDI² and ETTA MAMANG SANGADJI³

^{1,2}Department of Management, Faculty of Economy and Business, Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia.

³Post Graduate Program, Universitas PGRI Wiranegara, Indonesia.

*Corresponding Author Email: sopiah.fe@um.ac.id

Abstract

Organizational effectiveness and efficiency highly depend on the empowerment of human resources, perceived organizational support of its members, and job satisfaction. This paper aims to explain the indirect and direct impacts of lecturer empowerment and perceived organizational support on intention to stay, mediated by lecturers' job satisfaction in Indonesia. The data were collected from 320 lecturers; from 4 public universities and 10 private universities in Indonesia, obtained through closed questionnaire with 5 alternative answers, and data analysis using Warp PLS. The findings of the research show that all research hypotheses are accepted, meaning that employee empowerment and perceived organizational support (POS) have positive and significant influence directly and indirectly toward lecturers' intention to stay in organization through job satisfaction. For organizational practice, this research provides insights to emphasize the importance empowerment of lecturers, perceived organizational support (POS), and job satisfaction to maintain lecturers' planning to stay in the university.

Keywords: Intention to Stay, Lecturer empowerment, Perceived Organizational Support and Job Satisfaction.

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources in an organization have strategic and crucial role which determine the efficiency and effectiveness of an organization. Furthermore, employee performance contributes significantly to organizational performance. Therefore, the competent, excellent, and high-performing human resources qualify or even should be maintained in an organization. In order to maintain the human resources, particular strategies and policies related to employee empowerment and perceived organizational support of its employees should be carried out to make the employees satisfied and have intention to stay in their organization (Johari et al., 2012; Tepeci, 2001). Employee empowerment is one of the methods or strategies utilized to produce excellent and high-performing employees, enabling them to develop their confidence by appreciating their skills (Sedarmayanti, 2017). According to (Ivanova & von Scheve, 2020), the concept of employee empowerment has become the main concern of policy makers in the practice of human resource management in organizations related to the realizing the goals of organization's and company's competitiveness (Lassoued et al., 2020). To improve the empowerment of lecturer employees, institutions/universities seek to provide good information related to the duties and responsibilities of lecturers, provide feedback on performance appraisals that have been carried out, and disseminate information about the vision, mission and organizational goals having a significant impact on job satisfaction (Idris et al., 2018). Another studies also revealed that psychologically empowering employees has an impact on improving the harmonious relationship between lecturers and institutions, and giving rise to

positive responses and attitudes of lecturers towards work; raises high responsibility for the duties and obligations of lecturers at the Institute (Pelit et al., 2011; Widodo, 2015; Yuliandi & Tahir, 2019); improve lecturer communication and participation, raise lecturers' self-confidence and independence, and contribute to increasing job satisfaction, performance and lecturers' intention not to leave and lecturers' intention to be committed to the organization (Chinomona et al., 2017; Valdez et al., 2019).

This research model was built by adopting, we use the Social exchange theory "reciprocity principle - which emphasizes the existence of satisfying and beneficial social exchanges between two parties, namely lecturers and institutions/universities. Lecturers give all their time, energy, abilities, knowledge, experience for the organization/university. Likewise, organizations/universities try their best to fulfill all the needs and desires of lecturers. This theory is supported by several studies of (Hong et al., 2012; Jyoti et al., 2021). This study aims to produce an Intention to Stay Model built by the variables of employee empowerment, perceived organizational support (POS) and job satisfaction of lecturers.

The novelty of this research are: (1) Research on the Intention to stay model which is built by empowering lecturers, organizational support perceived by lecturers and lecturers' job satisfaction in an integrated manner designed from 4 variables is still rare in existing literature, previous research is still partially done. (2) The previous literature on this theme/topic was mostly carried out in the context of business organizations, while this research focused on the world of education related to lecturers, both lecturers at public and private universities in Indonesia (3) There is a literature gap of the four variables studied, so it is still research needs to be done to strengthen and develop existing research results.

By producing the Intention to stay model and understanding the factors causing it, this research is expected to contribute to: (1) the enrichment of literatures of Human Resources Science related to the intention to stay model; (2) Recommendation to management level of higher education institutions in Indonesia to make effective policies to retain lecturers by recognizing the importance of empowering lecturers and organizational support to increase lecturers' job satisfaction.

2. LITERATUR REVIEW

In the millennial era or generation Z as it is today, maintaining or retaining competent employees to stay and survive in the organization is not an easy job, even it requires serious efforts. One way that organizations can do is to empower employees so that they have the ability to make decisions independently (Haas, 2010), without the help of other people/leaders (Ivanova & von Scheve, 2020). Structural empowerment is intended as a serious effort by organizations to build and improve effective communication and full involvement of employees in a decision made by organization (Monje Amor et al., 2020). Meanwhile, psychological empowerment/employee empowerment is intended as an effort made by the organization to increase employee motivation and performance, with the fulfillment of employee autonomy needs (Suifan et al., 2020); need for affiliation (Fock et al., 2011); increase job satisfaction due to clarity of purpose and availability of work-related information and can

increase the relationship between the two parties (Idris et al., 2018); increase job satisfaction because communication in the organization goes well/effectively (Valdez et al., 2019). This research model conceptualizes the impact of employee empowerment on job satisfaction and employee intention to stay within the organization. This model is based on previous studies conducted by (Ali et al., 2017; Chen & Yu, 2014; Haque & Aslam, 2014; Ramalho Luz et al., 2018; Sule, 2017; Yücel, 2012).

Organizational support theory describes that employees perceive the effort made by the organization to fulfill economic and social needs, realizing them to perform optimally to achieve organizational goals (Worku, 2015); is an important construct in the relationship between employees and the company. Perceived organizational support (POS) is an employee's perception of the amount of attention, effort and support the organization provides in paying employee contributions. Competent and high-performing employees deserve to be retained. There are several ways that organizations can do, including by providing maximum support for employees. Perceived organizational support is interpreted as a form of support provided by the organization to develop and mature employees in both personally and professionally, and those was perceived by employees as real.

This can be realized if the needs and desires of employees are met - it can be material or immaterial (Chinomona et al., 2017; Choi & Chiu, 2017; Varma et al., 2020). The main antecedent of job satisfaction is POS (Karatepe, 2012; Mabasa & Ngirande, 2015). On the other hand, low organizational support for employees has an impact on employees' high intention to leave the organization (Worku, 2015). According to social exchange theory, POS increases employee intention to stay with the organization (Lu et al., 2019). The direct impact of high POS is employee's job satisfaction (Cicolini et al., 2014). Researchers conducted by (Han et al., 2015; Li et al., 2019; Olayiwola, 2016) found that the biggest contribution of employees' intention to stay in the organization is job satisfaction. Their research is also supported by several studies, including: (Cao et al., 2014; Hakkak et al., 2014; Perryer et al., 2010; Thevanes & Saranraj, 2018; Ukil, 2016). In line with this statement, the research of (Cao et al., 2014; Hakkak et al., 2014; Islam et al., 2013; Meng, 2010; Perryer et al., 2010) also proved that POS positively affects employees' intention to stay with the organization.

3. METHODS

3.1 Research Design

Quantitative approach with explanation type of research is applied in this research. The research framework is illustrated as follows:

Figure 1: Research Framework

3.2 Data

This research was conducted on all non-civil servant lecturers, institutional lecturers, and special lecturers in 4 public universities and 10 private universities in the area of Kota, Malang Regency, Batu, Pasuruan, and Probolinggo in East Java, Indonesia. The sampling technique applied in this research is proportional random sampling. The data collection methods used are closed instrument, conducted for 4 months from February to May 2022, through two methods: 55% offline and 45% online by filling out the provided form. The instrument used in this research is a closed questionnaire with 5 alternative answers ranging from 1 (highly agree) to 5 (highly disagree). The respondents were asked to fill out the questionnaire without having to worry about privacy and mentioning their name. The research samples consist of 320 lecturers.

3.3 Variable Measurement

This study consists of 4 variables, namely 2 exogenous variables (Employee empowerment and Perceived Organizational Support), 1 intervening variable, namely Job satisfaction (Z) and 1 variable endogenous, namely Intention to stay. (1)Employee empowerment is measured by adopting and modifying Idris et.Al. (2018). (2) Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is measured by measuring the adoption and modification of Cheng et al. (2013). (3) Job satisfaction is measured by adopting and modifying (Ganji & Johnson, 2020). (4) Intention to stay is measured by adopting and modifying (Ahanchian & Ganji, 2017).

3.4 Data Analysis

Data analysis carried out in this study included: (1) Descriptive statistical analysis was used with the help of SPSS version 21.0, to explain the conditions/descriptions of 4 research variables, namely 2 exogenous variables, 1 intervening variable and 1 endogenous variable. (2) Partial Least Square analysis, Warp PLS version 7.0., by performing: (a) Evaluation of the outer model, to test the validity of indicators of all research variables. (b) Evaluation of the inner model, to test the reliability of the instrument. (c) Hypothesis Testing, to decide whether the formulated hypothesis is accepted or rejected.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Respondent's demographic factors

Respondent's demographic factors can be explained by the following table:

Table 1: Respondent's demographic factors

Respondent's demographic factors	Frequency	Percentage
Gender :		
Female	154	48%
Male	166	52%
Age:		
27-37 years old	182	57%
38-48 years old	115	40%
More than 49 years old	23	7%
Education:		
Master	225	70%
Ph.D./DR	95	30%
Experience		
5-10 years	134	42%
10-15 years	112	35%
More than 15 years	74	23%
Sum	320	100 %
University:		
Public	5	33%
Private	10	67%

Table 1 above explains that Respondent's demographic factors: the majority of respondents (52%) are male; aged 27-37 years (57%); the majority have master's degree education (70%); Most (42%) of the respondents have worked for a maximum of 10 years. ; the majority (67%) came from private universities.

4.2. The result of descriptive statistics

Table 2 below shows the results of descriptive statistical tests, as follows:

Table 2: The Result of Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive Statistics						
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
X1	320	28.00	50.00	41.3374	.18463	3.30276
X2	320	29.00	45.00	37.7843	.24514	4.38514
Z	320	30.00	50.00	41.6749	.22321	3.99299
Y	320	29.00	45.00	37.6155	.24640	4.40773
Valid N (list wise)	320					

Table 2: Shows that:

1) Employee empowerment variable (X1) is categorized as good/high with the minimum statistic score of 28.0, maximum statistic score of 50.0, and mean score of 41.3374. It means that employee empowerment is perceived by lecturers in Indonesia as high.

2) Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is categorized as high with the minimum statistic score of 29.0, maximum statistic score of 45.0, and mean score of 37.7843. It is concluded that Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is perceived high by the lecturers.

3) Job satisfaction is categorized as high with the minimum statistic score of 30.0, maximum statistic score of 50.0, and mean score of 41.6749. It is concluded that job satisfaction is perceived as high by the lecturers.

4) Intention to stay is categorized as high/good with the minimum statistic score of 29.0, maximum statistic score of 45.0, and mean score of 37.6155.

4.3. Analysis result of Warp PLS

4.3.1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is used to measure the validity of the instruments by considering their loading factor score. The result of the convergent validity is as follows:

Table 3: Convergent Validity

No	Variable	Item	Loading Factor	SE	P Value	Validity
1	Employee Empowerment (X1)	X1.1	0.830	0.069	<0.001	Valid
		X1.2	0.775	0.071	<0.001	Valid
		X1.3	0.630	0.083	<0.001	Valid
		X1.4.	0.774	0.681	<0.001	Valid
		X1.5	0.843	0.801	<0.001	Valid
2	POS (X2)	X2.1	0.630	0.071	<0.001	Valid
		X2.2	0.724	0.073	<0.001	Valid
		X2.3	0.702	0.664	<0.001	Valid
		X2.4	0.721	0.075	<0.001	Valid
		X25.	0.732	0.074	0.001	Valid
		X2.6	0.802	0.073	<0.001	Valid
3	Job Satisfaction (Z)	Z.1	0.751	0.070	<0.001	Valid
		Z.2	0.704	0.073	<0.001	Valid
		Z.3	0.725	0.671	<0.001	Valid
		Z.4	0.733	0.801	0.001	Valid
4	Intention to Stay (Y)	Y.1	0.720	0.073	<0.001	Valid
		Y.2	0.723	0.674	<0.001	Valid
		Y.3	0.738	0.079	<0.001	Valid
		Y.4	0.805	0.084	0.001	Valid

The table 3 above shows that all question items from the 4 variables have the factor loading scores greater than 0.6 (> 0.6). Therefore, all questions items from the 4 variables are valid.

The second technique is carried out in order to determine the validity by considering the AVE score. The following is the result of the test:

Table 4: The AVE score

No.	Variable	AVE Score	Standard AVE	Validity
1	Employee Empowerment (X1)	0.537	0.5	Valid
2	POS (X2)	0.519	0.5	Valid
3	Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.535	0.5	Valid
4	Intention to Stay(Y)	0.531	0.5	Valid

Table 4 shows the results that all of the AVE score of the 4 variables are greater than 0.5 (> 0.5), all items from the 4 variables are valid.

4.3.2 Internal consistency reliability

Internal consistency reliability test is used to determine if all items from the 4 variables are reliable while they are considered reliable if their composite reliability score more than 0.7 (> 0.7). As result, the summary of internal consistency reliability test is presented as follows:

Table 5: Internal Consistency Reliability Test

No.	Variable	Cronbach Alpha Score	Composite Reliability	Reliability
1	Employee Empowerment (X1)	0.753	0.852	Reliable
2	POS (X2)	0.724	0.866	Reliable
3	Job Satisfaction (Z)	0.714	0.851	Reliable
4	Intention to Stay (Y)	0.741	0.863	Reliable

The table 5. Above shows that all items from the 4 variables are reliable because their composite reliability score is greater than 0.7 (> 0.7).

4.3.3. Result of Goodness of Fit (GoF) Test of the Model

GoF Test is employed to determine how closely observed exogenous variables used in this research (employee empowerment and perceived organizational support) mirrors the variability of endogenous variable (intention to stay). The result of GoF measurement can be seen in the following table:

Table 6: The Result of Goodness of Fit Model (GoF) test

No	Model Fit and Quality Indices	Result	Result Criteria	Acceptability
1	Average path coefficient (APC)	0.440, P<0.001	P-Value <5%	Accepted
2	Average R-squared (ARS)	0.395, P<0.001	P-Value <5%	Accepted
3	Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)	0.389, P<0.001	P-Value <5%	Accepted
4	Average Block VIF (AVIF)	1.549	acceptable if ≤ 5 (ideal ≤ 3.3)	Accepted
5	Average Full Collinearity VIF (AFVIF)	1.780	acceptable if ≤ 5 (ideal ≤ 3.3)	Accepted
6	Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)	0.458	small ≥ 0.1 , medium ≥ 0.25 , large ≥ 0.36	Accepted
7	Simpson's Paradox Ratio (SPR)	1.000	acceptable if ≥ 0.7 (ideal = 1)	Accepted
8	R-squared Contribution Ratio (RSCR)	1.000	acceptable if ≥ 0.9 (ideal = 1)	Accepted
9	Statistical Suppression Ratio (SSR)	1.000	acceptable if ≥ 0.7	Accepted
10	Nonlinear Bivariate Causality Direction Ratio (NLBCDR)	1.000	acceptable if ≥ 0.7	Accepted

Table 6. Above shows that the result of all Goodness of Fit Model (GoF) test fulfil the set standard. Therefore, the PLS model in this research is acceptable.

4.3.4. Hypotheses Test Result

The following is the recapitulation of the hypotheses test result:

Table 7: Hypotheses Test Result

Variable	Influence	Direct Influence	Indirect Influence	Total Influence	Acceptability
Employee Empowerment (X1)	X1 → Z	0.85		0.85	Accepted
Perceived Organizational Support (X2)	X1 → Y	0.20		0.20	Accepted
Job Satisfaction (Z)	Z → Y	0.13		0.13	Accepted
	X1 → Z → Y		0.85 x 0.13 = 0.111	0.111	Accepted
Intention to Stay (Y)	X2 → Z	0.12		0.12	Accepted
	X2 → Y	0.25		0.25	Accepted

	X ² → Z → Y		0.12 x 0.13 = 0.016	0.016	Accepted
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5. DISCUSSION

5.1 Lecturer Empowerment, Job Satisfaction, Intention to stay

The research findings prove that: (1) Lecturer empowerment in Indonesia is categorized as high. The lecturer is confident that he has carried out the tri dharma¹ (lecturing, researching, and social empowering) of higher education well because he feels he has adequate competence; lecturers believe that the leadership appreciates the achievement of their good performance; the leadership appreciates the creativity/innovation of the lecturers at work; and leaders appreciate the independence of lecturers in their work. (2) Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is perceived by high lecturers.

This means that the University/institution supports and provides assistance if needed; the leadership is proud of the achievements of the lecturers, the leadership is concerned and concerned with the welfare of the lecturers, appreciates the efforts of the lecturers to continue the process to achieve progress in themselves and their careers, and the leaders respect the values and beliefs held by the lecturers. (3) Job satisfaction is perceived by high lecturers. This means that lecturers in Indonesia are satisfied with their work, love their work, are comfortable in their work, and are happy with their work. 4) Intention to stay, categorized as high. This means that the lecturer is comfortable with his current job, does not want to move to another job or another institution/university, and has no intention of changing jobs, both in the short term and in the future. (5) Empowerment of lecturers have an effect on the intention of lecturers to stay at the institution/university. (6) Job satisfaction plays a role as partial mediating in the association between lecturer empowerment and the lecturers' intention to stay at the university.

The essence of lecturer empowerment (both structural and psychological empowerment) can be interpreted as the extent to which lecturers are motivated, facilitated to be able to make decisions independently (Haas, 2010), without direct or indirect involvement/involvement of leadership such as the dean or rector as the highest leader of the university/institution (Ivanova & von Scheve, 2020); so that communication within the organization goes well and increases the involvement of lecturers in organizational decision making (Monje Amor et al., 2020); for increasing task intensity and self-motivation by satisfying employee autonomy needs (Oluwaseun, 2016; Pelit et al., 2011); provide a sense of affiliation, increase employee engagement with work (Karatepe, 2012; Mabasa & Ngirande, 2015); increase employee job satisfaction (Idris et al., 2018); amplifying the association between lecturers and departments/faculties/universities, and improving the relationship between lecturers and work (Idris et al., 2018); improve good communication between lecturers and colleagues and/or leaders (Valdez et al., 2019); have an effect on the intention to stay in the university (Ali et al., 2017; Oluwaseun, 2016). Other researchers (Chen & Yu, 2014; Haque & Aslam, 2014; Ramalho Luz et al., 2018; Sule, 2017; Yang & Lee, 2009; Yücel, 2012) also prove that the

intention of the lecturer/employee to stay at the university/institution is influenced by the job satisfaction of the lecturer/employee.

5.2 Intention to Stay, Perceived Organizational Support, Job Satisfaction

The research findings prove that intention to stay is influenced directly by perceived organizational support and indirectly through job satisfaction for lecturers in Indonesia. According to this theory, when lecturers/employees feel that the needs and desires (material and non-material) are fulfilled by the organization to the fullest, self-awareness will appear in employees to perform optimally to achieve organizational goals (Worku, 2015). Organizational support theory is used in this study.

According to this theory, when lecturers/employees feel that the needs and desires (material and non-material) are fulfilled by the organization to the fullest, self-awareness will appear in employees to perform optimally to achieve organizational goals (Worku, 2015); is an important construct in the relationship between employees and the company. Organizational support perceived by lecturers is defined as the sensed perception of a lecturer regarding the amount of attention, effort and support given by the university in paying lecturers' contributions to the university; refers to the feeling felt by lecturers that the university/organization values their contributions and refers to the feeling felt by lecturers that the university/organization appreciates the contribution that lecturers make to the university by trying to meet their inner and outer needs (Chinomona et al., 2017; Varma et al., 2020). The main antecedent of job satisfaction is POS (Karatepe, 2012; Mabasa & Ngirande, 2015).

The high level of absenteeism of lecturers/employees, the emergence of the intention of lecturers/employees to move or leave the organization indicates a low level of POS (Worku, 2015). According to social exchange theory, POS tends to be more likely to cause employee attachment to work and the organization and increase the intention to stay in the organization (Lu et al., 2019). While job satisfaction or job dissatisfaction can be interpreted as the level of feeling that the lecturer is satisfied or not. otherwise unsatisfactory related to work, for example feeling satisfied / dissatisfied with the work itself, promotion in work, opportunities for personal and professional growth and development, working conditions, compensation, harmonious relationships with colleagues and or leaders, assessments made by universities, and etc. (Cicolini et al., 2014). Researches by (Hakkak et al., 2014; Olayiwola, 2016; Rousseau, 2006; Ukil, 2016) proves that job satisfaction can predict the intention to stay positively. Their research is also supported by: (Cao et al., 2014; Thevanes & Saranraj, 2018). In line with the finding, researches by (Meng, 2010; Perryer et al., 2010), also proves that perceived organizational support (POS) has effects on the intention to stay directly or indirectly via job satisfaction.

6. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper's objection is to explain the direct and indirect impacts of lecturer empowerment and perceived organizational support (POS) on intention to stay, mediated by a variable of lecturers' job satisfaction in Indonesia and examines the role of job satisfaction as a mediator in this relationship. The results of the study prove that there are direct and indirect effects of lecturer empowerment and perceived organizational support (POS) on intention to stay, mediated by a variable of lecturers' job satisfaction in Indonesia. Thus the leadership of the university/institution to pay more attention to and improve efforts to empower lecturers and employees in general and organizational support for lecturers/employees because it is empirically proven to have an impact on employee intentions to remain in the organization/university.

Acknowledgements

We would like to show our appreciation and gratitude to the Dean of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Malang, Head of the Research Institute and Community Service, State University of Malang for material and non-material support for the success of this article. May God repay your kindness?

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